

Chalcones VI. Synthesis of Some 4'-Fluorochalcones, Heterocyclic and Polynuclear Chalcone Analogues†

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Interest in the synthesis of substituted chalcones and heterocyclic chalcone analogues arose because of their promise as antimicrobial agents^{1-8,10-20}. These reports prompted us to synthesise thirteen new chalcones, described herein, with a view to study their antibacterial and antifungal activity. It was thought that the antimicrobial activity might be enhanced by the presence of *p*-fluoro substituent in the ketone component of the chalcone molecule, and/or by substitution, in place of the aromatic ring of the aldehydic component, with a polynuclear or a heterocyclic ring.

R = Aryl (compounds : I-IX, XII and XIII)
= Heteroaromatic (X and XI)

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Chalcones designed in this way were prepared by the Claisen-Schmidt condensation of 4-fluoroacetophenone with various aromatic and heteroaromatic aldehydes, in the presence of aqueous-alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution as the condensing agent. In general the yields of chalcones were good, in some cases approaching almost the theoretical. In the case of 4'-fluoro-3-hydroxy-4-methoxy-chalcone (V) and pyrrole analogue of 4'-fluoro-chalcone (XI), however, the yields were rather poor. The chalcones described in this communication are characterized by their vivid halochromic effects when wetted with concentrated sulphuric acid.

These chalcones were assayed, concentration : 100 μ g/ml. of 50% aqueous-ethanol, against the following bacteria and fungi respectively : *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salomonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*, *Candidia albicans*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Microsporum canis* and *Aspergillus niger*. But none of these compounds possessed any antibacterial or antifungal activity.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points were taken on Mel-Temp. and are uncorrected. Silica Gel 'G' (Merck) was used for thin-layer-chromatography. *p*-Fluoroacetophenone used was of Eastman Organic Chemicals (U.S.A.), laboratory Reagent grade.

TABLE I

4'-Fluorochalcones

Comp. No.	R =	Yield %	Colour, Crystalline shape	M.P. °C	Halo-chromism with conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Molecular Formula	Analysis*			
							%C	%H	Calcd.	Found
I	2-Cl-	75	White prismatic needles.	87	Yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ OClF	69.11	69.79	3.87	3.60
II	4-Cl-	73	White prismatic needles.	136	Orange	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ OClF	69.11	68.89	3.87	4.30
III	2,3-(OCH ₃) ₂ -	79	Pale yellow prismatic needles.	69	Reddish-Brown	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ F	71.32	71.01	5.28	5.40
IV	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -	70	Yellow crystalline solid.	82	Red	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ F	71.32	70.96	5.28	5.00
V	3-(OH)-4-(OCH ₃)-	33	Dirty yellow clusters of prismatic needles.	117	Red	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ F	70.58	70.20	4.81	5.00
VI	5-Br-2,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -	51	Pale yellow clusters of needles.	139	Dark red	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃ BrF	55.91	55.62	3.86	3.91
VII	6-Br-2,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -	68	Yellow prismatic needles.	164	Dark red	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃ BrF	55.91	56.23	3.86	3.80
VIII	3-NO ₂ -	55	Dirty yellow non-descript solid.	166	Yellowish brown	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ NO ₃ F	66.42	65.97	3.72	3.89
IX	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ -	90	Yellow rectangular plates.	110	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ NOF	75.81	75.82	5.99	6.90

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The chalcones were prepared according to the method of Geissman and Clinton⁹, and were purified in the usual way. The check on the purity was made by thin-layer chromatography on silica gel, using petroleum ether (40–60°) ethyl acetate as the developer solvents. The spots on T.L.C. plates could be located clearly by virtue of their yellow colour. Sometimes, however, the exposure of the TLC plates to iodine vapours was found to be advantageous.

Tables 1 and 2 list the fluoro-chalcones prepared in the course of present study, and these were crystallised from ethanol unless otherwise stated.

TABLE 2

Chalcone Analogues

Comp. No.	R =	Yield %	Colour, Crystalline shape	M.P. °C	Halo-chromism with conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Molecular Formula	Analysis*			
							%C		%H	
							Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
X	2-Furyl-	59	Pale yellow clusters of needles.	68	Dark brown	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ F	72.22	72.22	4.19	4.17
XI	2-Pyrrolyl-	30	Yellow rectangular plates**	160	Dark red	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NOF	72.55	72.75	4.68	4.88
XII	1-Naphthyl-	93	Pale yellow mica like flakes.	92	Violet	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ OF	82.59	82.79	4.74	5.00
XIII	9-Anthracyl-	98	Yellow prismatic needles.	131	Dark green	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ OF	84.64	84.86	4.63	4.12

* In the elemental analysis of these fluoro-chalcones, the usual tube filling was modified, in order to check the fluorine from passing through. The modification²¹ involved consisted in the substitution of a portion of the copper oxide-lead chromate mixture with two small sections of magnesium oxide.

** Crystallised from benzene.

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